

**BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIMDA IQTISODIY SAVODXONLIK VA
MATEMATIKANING INTEGRATSIYASI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich ta'limda moliyaviy savodxonlik va matematikaning integratsiyalashuvi o'rganilib, moliyaviy tushunchalarni erta yoshda o'rgatish muhimligi ta'kidlangan. Unda matematik ko'nikmalarni asosiy moliyaviy bilimlar bilan uyg'unlashtirish yosh o'quvchilarga byudjet tuzish, tejash va foiz stavkalarini tushunish kabi amaliy pul boshqaruv qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga qanday yordam berishi mumkinligi muhokama qilinadi. Misollar va tadbirlar orqali maqola talabalar qo'shish, ayirish, ko'paytirish va foizlar kabi matematik operatsiyalarni haqiqiy moliyaviy vaziyatlarda qanday qo'llashi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Maqolada moliyaviy savodxonlikni matematika bilan uyg'unlashtirish boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini kelajakdagi moliyaviy farovonlik uchun zaruriy ko'nikmalar bilan qurollantiradi, degan xulosaga keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Moliyaviy savodxonlik, boshlang'ich ta'lim, matematika, byudjet, jamg'arma, foizlar, oddiy qiziqish, qaror qabul qilish qobiliyati, pulni boshqarish, erta ta'lim.

**ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ С
МАТЕМАТИКОЙ В НАЧАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ**

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Аннотация: В этой статье исследуется интеграция финансовой грамотности и математики в начальное образование, подчеркивая важность

преподавания финансовых концепций в раннем возрасте. В нем обсуждается, как сочетание математических навыков с базовыми финансовыми знаниями может помочь юным ученикам развить практические способности управления деньгами, такие как составление бюджета, сбережения и понимание процентных ставок. На примерах и упражнениях статья демонстрирует, как учащиеся могут применять математические операции, такие как сложение, вычитание, умножение и проценты, в реальных финансовых ситуациях. В статье делается вывод, что сочетание финансовой грамотности с математикой дает учащимся начальных классов навыки, необходимые для их будущего финансового благополучия.

Ключевые слова: Финансовая грамотность, начальное образование, математика, бюджетирование, сбережения, проценты, простые проценты, навыки принятия решений, управление деньгами, дошкольное образование.

INTEGRATING FINANCIAL LITERACY WITH MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article explores the integration of financial literacy and mathematics in primary education, highlighting the importance of teaching financial concepts at an early age. It discusses how combining mathematical skills with basic financial knowledge can help young learners develop practical money management abilities, such as budgeting, saving, and understanding interest rates. Through examples and activities, the article demonstrates how students can apply mathematical operations like addition, subtraction, multiplication, and percentages to real-life financial situations. The article concludes that combining financial literacy with

mathematics equips primary school students with essential skills for their future financial well-being.

Keywords: Financial literacy, primary education, mathematics, budgeting, saving, percentages, simple interest, decision-making skills, money management, early education.

Introduction In today's world, financial literacy is an essential skill that helps individuals make informed decisions about money management, savings, investments, and budgeting. While financial literacy is often associated with adulthood, introducing basic financial concepts at an early age can significantly shape a child's understanding of money. Integrating mathematics into financial literacy education in primary schools not only enhances mathematical skills but also empowers students with the tools needed to manage their future finances. This article explores the benefits of combining mathematics and financial literacy in primary education and provides examples of how these subjects can be integrated effectively.

The Importance of Early Financial Literacy Education

Financial decisions made early in life can have a lasting impact on individuals' financial well-being. By integrating financial literacy into primary education, children can develop good money habits, learn how to set goals, and understand basic economic concepts like saving, spending, and budgeting. At the same time, mathematical skills such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and percentages are crucial in understanding these financial concepts.

Introducing financial literacy in primary education helps students understand that money is not infinite and that choices have consequences. When mathematical concepts are used to teach financial literacy, it creates a more engaging and practical learning experience. It also helps students see how mathematics applies to real-world situations, making the subject more relevant and meaningful.

How Mathematics Can Enhance Financial Literacy in Primary Schools

1. Understanding Money and Basic Transactions

One of the simplest ways to introduce financial literacy through mathematics is by teaching students the value of money and how to perform basic transactions. For example, students can use coins and bills to practice addition and subtraction. By using play money in classroom activities, they can understand how to count change, make purchases, and see the value of different denominations. This allows them to apply addition and subtraction in a real-world context.

Example: If a student buys an item for \$3.50 and pays with a \$5 bill, they will subtract \$3.50 from \$5 to determine how much change they should receive.

2. Budgeting and Saving

Teaching primary students how to create a simple budget is an effective way to combine financial literacy with mathematics. A budget requires students to add up their income (or allowances) and subtract their expenses to determine how much they can save. These basic operations help students develop a sense of responsibility for managing money and setting financial goals.

Example: If a student receives \$10 as an allowance and spends \$4 on snacks and \$3 on toys, they can subtract $\$4 + \3 from \$10 to see how much money is left to save or spend later.

3. Percentages and Discounts

Percentages are a core concept in both mathematics and financial literacy. By teaching primary school students how to calculate percentages, teachers can help them understand discounts, tax rates, and interest on savings or loans. Simple examples, such as calculating a 10% discount on an item, can make learning percentages fun and practical.

Example: If a toy costs \$20 and is on sale for 10% off, the student will multiply \$20 by 10% (or 0.1) to calculate the discount amount of \$2. They can then subtract \$2 from \$20 to determine the sale price of \$18.

4. Saving for Goals

Teaching primary students about saving for a specific goal, like buying a toy or going on a trip, is a valuable exercise. By setting a target amount and figuring out how

much they need to save each week, students practice division and addition while learning the importance of delayed gratification. This helps them understand the relationship between time, money, and saving.

Example: If a student wants to buy a toy worth \$30 and saves \$5 each week, they can divide \$30 by \$5 to determine how many weeks it will take to reach their goal. In this case, the answer is 6 weeks.

5. Simple Interest and Savings Growth

Introducing the basic idea of saving and earning interest is another excellent way to integrate mathematics with financial literacy. Teachers can use simple interest calculations to show how money can grow over time in a savings account. Using basic multiplication, students can understand how interest works.

Example: If a student deposits \$10 into a savings account that earns 5% interest each year, the student can multiply \$10 by 0.05 to calculate \$0.50 in interest for the first year.

Benefits of Integrating Financial Literacy with Mathematics

1. Real-Life Application of Math

When students see how mathematical concepts apply to everyday situations, such as saving money or calculating discounts, they are more likely to engage with the subject. This connection makes mathematics less abstract and more meaningful.

2. Early Development of Good Money Habits

Learning how to manage money at a young age fosters responsible financial behavior later in life. By understanding basic financial concepts like budgeting and saving, students are better prepared to handle more complex financial decisions as they grow older.

3. Improved Decision-Making Skills

By integrating math and financial literacy, students learn to make informed decisions. They can analyze costs, evaluate savings options, and make choices based on their goals. These skills are valuable not only for personal finance but also for critical thinking and problem-solving in general.

Conclusion The integration of financial literacy and mathematics in primary education provides students with essential skills that will serve them throughout their lives. By introducing basic financial concepts through mathematical exercises, students can learn how to manage money, create budgets, calculate percentages, and save for their goals. As they apply these skills in real-life scenarios, they develop both financial competence and mathematical confidence. By teaching financial literacy and mathematics together, we are preparing students for a successful financial future and helping them become responsible, informed citizens in a complex economic world.

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